

Differential Sandwich Theorems for p-valent Analytic Functions Defined by Cho–Kwon–Srivastava Operator

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Abstract.

By using of Cho–Kwon–Srivastava operator, we obtain some subordinations and superordinations results for certain normalized p-valent analytic functions.

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1. Introduction.

Let $H(U)$ be the class of analytic functions in the open unit disk $U = \{z \in \mathbb{C} : |z| < 1\}$, and let $H[a; p]$ be the subclass of $H(U)$ consisting of functions of the form :

$$f(z) = a + a_p z^p + a_{p+1} z^{p+1} + \dots \quad (a \in \mathbb{C}),$$

For simplicity, $H[a] = H[a; 1]$. Also, let $A(p)$ denote the class of functions $f(z)$ of the form

$$(1.1) \quad f(z) = z^p + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n z^{n+p}. \quad (p \in \mathbb{N} = \{1, 2, \dots\}),$$

Which are analytic and p-valent in U .

If $f, g \in H(U)$, we say that the function f is subordinate to g , or the function g is superordinate to f , if there exists a Schwarz function ω , i.e., $\omega \in H(U)$ with $\omega(0) = 0$ and $|\omega(z)| < 1, z \in U$, such that $f(z) = g(\omega(z))$ for all $z \in U$. This subordination is usually denoted by $f(z) \prec g(z)$. It is well known that, if the function g is univalent in U , then $f(z) \prec g(z)$ is equivalent to $f(0) = g(0)$ and $f(U) \subset g(U)$ (cf., e.g., [9], see also [5]).

Supposing that p, h are two analytic functions in U , let

$$\varphi(r, s, t; z) : C^3 \times U \rightarrow C.$$

If $p(z)$ and $\varphi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2 p''(z); z)$ are univalent functions in U and $p(z)$ satisfies the second-order differential subordination

$$(1.2) \quad h(z) \prec \varphi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2 p''(z); z),$$

then $p(z)$ is called to be a solution of the differential superordination (1.2). An analytic function $q(z)$ is called a subordinator of the solution of the differential superordination (1.2), if $q(z) \prec p(z)$ for all the functions $p(z)$ satisfying (1.2). A univalent subordinator $\tilde{q}$ that satisfies $q(z) \prec \tilde{q}(z)$ for all of the subordinants q of (1.2), is called the best subordinator (cf., e.g., [9], see also [5]).

Recently, Miller and Mocanu [10] obtained sufficient conditions on the functions h, q and φ for which the following implication holds:

$$h(z) \prec \varphi(p(z), zp'(z), z^2 p''(z); z) \Rightarrow q(z) \prec p(z).$$

For functions $f_j(z) \in A(p)$, given by

$$f_j(z) = z^p + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_{n,j} z^{n+p} \quad (j = 1, 2),$$

we define the Hadamard product (or convolution) of $f_1(z)$ and $f_2(z)$ by

$$(f_1 * f_2)(z) = z^p + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_{n,1} a_{n,2} z^{n+p} = (f_2 * f_1)(z) \quad (z \in U).$$

In terms of the Pochhammer symbol $(\theta)_n$ given by

$$(\theta)_n = \begin{cases} 1, & (n = 0) \\ \theta(\theta+1)\dots(\theta+n-1), & (n \in N = \{1, 2, \dots\}), \end{cases}$$

we now define a function $\varphi_p(a, c; z)$ by

$$(1.3) \quad \varphi_p(a, c; z) = z^p + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(a)_n}{(c)_n} z^{n+p}$$

$$(a \in R; c \in R \setminus Z_0^-; Z_0^- = \{0, -1, -2, \dots\}; z \in U).$$

With the aid of the function $\varphi_p(a, c; z)$ defined by (1.3), we consider a function $\varphi_p^*(a, c; z)$ given by the following convolution

$$\varphi_p(a, c; z) * \varphi_p^*(a, c; z) = \frac{z^p}{(1-z)^{\lambda+p}} \quad (\lambda > -p; z \in U)$$

which yields the following family of linear operators $I_p^\lambda(a, c)$:

$$(1.4) \quad I_p^\lambda(a, c)f(z) = \varphi_p^*(a, c; z) * f(z) \quad (a, c \in \mathbb{R} \setminus \mathbb{Z}_0^-; \lambda > -p; z \in U).$$

For a function $f(z) \in A(p)$, given by (1.1), it is easily seen from (1.4) that

$$(1.5) \quad I_p^\lambda(a, c)f(z) = z^p + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{(c)_n (\lambda + p)_n}{(a)_n (1)_n} a_{p+n} z^{p+n} \quad (z \in U),$$

which readily yields the following properties of the operator $I_p^\lambda(a, c)$:

$$(1.6) \quad z \left(I_p^\lambda(a, c)f(z) \right)' = (\lambda + p) I_p^{\lambda+1}(a, c)f(z) - \lambda I_p^\lambda(a, c)f(z)$$

and

$$(1.7) \quad z \left(I_p^\lambda(a+1, c)f(z) \right)' = a I_p^\lambda(a, c)f(z) - (a-p) I_p^\lambda(a+1, c)f(z).$$

The operator $I_p^\lambda(a, c)$ was introduced and studied by Cho et al. [6].

We observe that:

$$I_p^0(p, 1)f(z) = I_p^1(p+1, 1)f(z) = f(z), I_p^1(p, 1)f(z) = \frac{zf'(z)}{p},$$

$$I_p^2(p, 1)f(z) = \frac{2zf'(z) + z^2f''(z)}{p(p+1)};$$

$$I_p^0(a+1, 1)f(z) = p \int_0^z \frac{f(t)}{p} dt,$$

$$I_p^n(a, a)f(z) = D^{n+p-1}f(z) \quad (n \in \mathbb{N}, n > -p),$$

Where $D^{n+p-1}f(z)$ is the Ruschewyh derivative of $(n+p-1)$ th order, see[8]. Many interesting result of multivalent analytic functions associated with the linear operator $I_p^\lambda(a, c)$ have been studied in [6].

Also we observe that:

$$(i) \quad I^0(1, 1)f(z) = I^1(2, 1)f(z) = f(z), I^1(1, 1)f(z) = zf'(z),$$

$$I^2(1, 1)f(z) = \frac{1}{2}(2zf'(z) + z^2f''(z));$$

$$(ii) \quad I^\mu(\mu+2, 1)f(z) = F_\mu(f)(z) (\mu > -1), \text{ where}$$

$$F_\mu(f)(z) = \frac{\mu+1}{z^\mu} \int_0^z t^{\mu-1} f(t) dt \quad (\text{see [3]});$$

$$(iii) \quad I^0(n+1, 1)f(z) = I_n f(z) (n \in N_0 = \mathbb{N} \cup \{0\}) \text{ (Noor integral operator, see [13]);}$$

$$(iv) \quad I^\lambda(\mu+2, 1)f(z) = I_{\lambda, \mu} f(z) (\lambda > -1; \mu > -2) \text{ (Choi - Saigo - Srivastava operator, see [7]).}$$

Recently many authors ([1], [11], [12] and [14]) have used the results of Bulboacă [4] and shown some sufficient conditions applying first order differential subordinations and superordinations.

The main object of the present paper is to find sufficient condition for certain normalized analytic functions $f(z), g(z)$ in U such that $I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z) \neq 0$ for $0 < |z| < 1$ and satisfy

$$q_1(z) \prec \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a, c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z)} \prec q_2(z),$$

where q_1, q_2 are given univalent functions in U . Also, we obtain the number of known results as their special cases.

2. Definitions and preliminaries.

In order to prove our results, we shall make use of the following known results.

Definition 1 ([9]). Denote by Q , the set of all functions f that are analytic and injective on $\bar{U} \setminus E(f)$, where

$$E(f) = \left\{ \zeta \in \partial U : \lim_{z \rightarrow \zeta} f(z) = \infty \right\}$$

and are such that

$$f'(\zeta) \neq 0 \text{ for } \zeta \in \partial U \setminus E(f).$$

Lemma 1 ([10]). Let q be univalent in the unit disk U and let θ and ϕ be analytic in a domain D containing $q(U)$ with $\phi(\omega) \neq 0$ when $\omega \in q(U)$. Set

$$\psi(z) = zq'(z)\phi(q(z)) \text{ and } h(z) = (q(z)) + \psi(z).$$

Suppose that

- (i) $\psi(z)$ is starlike univalent in U ,
- (ii) $\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{zh'(z)}{\psi(z)} \right\} > 0, z \in U$.

If p is analytic in U with $p(0) = q(0), p(U) \subseteq D$ and

$$(2.1) \quad \theta(p(z)) + zp'(z)\phi(p(z)) < \theta(q(z)) + zq'(z)\phi(q(z)),$$

then

$$p(z) \prec q(z)$$

and q is the best dominant.

Lemma 2 ([4]). Let q be convex univalent in the unit disk U and let θ and ϕ be analytic in a domain D containing $q(U)$. Suppose that

$$(i) \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{\theta'(q(z))}{\varphi(q(z))} \right\} > 0, \quad z \in U,$$

(ii) $\psi(z) = zq'(z)\varphi(q(z))$ is univalent in U .

If $p \in H[q(0), 1] \cap Q$ with $p(U) \subseteq D$ and $\theta(p(z)) + zp'(z)\varphi(p(z))$ is univalent in U and

$$(2.2) \quad \theta(q(z)) + zq'(z)\varphi(q(z)) \prec \theta(p(z)) + zp'(z)\varphi(p(z)),$$

then

$$q(z) \prec p(z),$$

and q is the best subordinator of (2.2).

3. Subordination results.

Using Lemma 1, we first prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1. Let $\alpha \neq 0, \beta > 0$ and $q(z)$ be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$. Further assume that

$$(3.1) \quad \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{\beta - p\alpha}{\alpha} + 2q(z) + \left(1 + \frac{zq''(z)}{q'(z)} \right) \right\} > 0 \quad (z \in U).$$

If $f, g \in A(p)$ satisfy

$$(3.2) \quad \gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z'(z),$$

Where

$$(3.3) \quad \begin{aligned} \gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta) = & (\beta - (p+1)\alpha) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a, c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z)} + \alpha \left(\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a, c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z)} \right)^2 \\ & + \alpha(\lambda + p + 1) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+2}(a, c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z)} \\ & - \alpha(\lambda + p) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a, c)g(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z)} \left(\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a, c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z)} \right), \end{aligned}$$

then

$$\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a, c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a, c)g(z)} \prec q(z)$$

And q is the best dominant.

Proof. Define the function $p(z)$ by

$$(3.4) \quad p(z) = \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)} \quad (z \in U).$$

Then the function $p(z)$ is analytic in U and $p(0) = 1$. Therefore, differentiating (3.4) logarithmically with respect to z and using the identity (1.6) in the resulting equation, we have

$$(3.5) \quad \begin{aligned} & \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)} \left[\beta - (p+1)\alpha + \alpha \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)} \right. \\ & \left. + \alpha(\lambda+p+1) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+2}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)} - \alpha(\lambda+p) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)g(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)} \right] \\ & = (\beta - p\alpha)p(z) + \alpha p^2(z) + \alpha z p'(z). \end{aligned}$$

By using (3.5) in (3.2), we have

$$(3.6) \quad (\beta - p\alpha)p(z) + \alpha p^2(z) + \alpha z p'(z) \prec (\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z).$$

By setting

$$\theta(\omega) = \alpha\omega^2 + (\beta - p\alpha)\omega \quad \text{and} \quad \varphi(\omega) = \alpha$$

we can easily observe that $\theta(\omega)$ and $\varphi(\omega)$ are analytic in $\mathbb{C} \setminus \{0\}$ and that $\varphi(\omega) \neq 0$. Hence the result now follows by using Lemma 1.

Remark 1. Putting $\lambda=0$, $a=c=1$ and taking $f(z) \equiv g(z)$ ($z \in U$) in Theorem 1, we obtain the result obtained by Murugusundaramoorthy and Magesh [9, Corollary 2.9].

Putting $f(z) \equiv g(z)$ ($z \in U$) in Theorem 1, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 1. Let $\alpha \neq 0, \beta > 0$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$ and (3.1) holds true. If $f \in A(p)$ satisfies

$$\begin{aligned} & (\beta - (p+1)\alpha) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)} + \alpha(\lambda+p+1) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+2}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)} - \alpha(\lambda+p-1) \left(\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)} \right)^2 \\ & \prec (\beta - p\alpha)(q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z)), \\ & \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)} \prec q(z) \end{aligned}$$

and q is the best dominant.

Putting $a = \mu + p + 1$ ($\mu > -(p+1)$) and $c = 1$ in Theorem 1, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 2. Let $\alpha \neq 0, \beta > 0$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$ and (3.1) holds true. If $f, g \in A(p)$ satisfy

$$\gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - (p+1)\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z)$$

where

$$(3.7) \quad \gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta) = (\beta - (p+1)\alpha) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1, \mu} f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda, \mu} g(z)} + \alpha \left(\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1, \mu} f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda, \mu} g(z)} \right)^2 \\ + \alpha(\lambda + p + 1) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+2, \mu} f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda, \mu} g(z)} - \alpha(\lambda + p) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1, \mu} f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda, \mu} g(z)} \left(\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1, \mu} f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda, \mu} g(z)} \right),$$

then

$$\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1, \mu} f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda, \mu} g(z)} \prec q(z),$$

and q is the best dominant.

Putting $a = \mu + p + 1$ ($\mu > -p$), $c = 1$ and $\lambda = \mu$ in Theorem 1, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 3. Let $\alpha \neq 0, \beta > 0$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$ and (3.1) holds true. If $f, g \in A(p)$ satisfy

$$\gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - \alpha + \alpha\mu)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z),$$

where

$$(3.8) \quad \gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta) = (\beta - \alpha + \alpha\mu) \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu, p}(g)(z)} + \alpha \left(\frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu, p}(g)(z)} \right)^2 \\ + \alpha \frac{zf'(z)}{F_{\mu, p}(g)(z)} - \alpha(\mu + p) \frac{g(z)}{F_{\mu, p}(g)(z)} \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu, p}(g)(z)}.$$

then

$$\frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu, p}g(z)} \prec q(z),$$

and q is the best dominant.

Corollary 4. Let $\alpha \neq 0, \beta > 0$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$ and (3.1) holds true. If $f \in A(p)$ satisfies

$$\gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z),$$

where

$$(3.9) \quad \gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta) = (\beta - \alpha + \alpha\mu) \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} + \alpha \frac{zf'(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} - \alpha(\mu + p - 1) \left(\frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} \right)^2$$

then

$$\frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} \prec q(z), \quad (\mu > -p),$$

and q is the best dominant.

4. Superordination and sandwich results.

Theorem 2. Let $\alpha \neq 0, \beta > 0$. Let q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$. Assume that

$$(4.1) \quad \operatorname{Re}\{q(z)\} \geq \operatorname{Re}\left\{ \frac{p\alpha - \beta}{(1+p)\alpha} \right\}.$$

Let $f, g \in A(p), \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)} \in H[q(0), 1] \cap Q$, Let $\gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ be univalent in U and

$$(4.2) \quad (\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z) \prec \gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta),$$

where $\gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.3), then

$$(4.3) \quad q(z) \prec \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)}.$$

and q is the best subordinant.

Proof. Let $p(z)$ be defined by (3.4). Therefore, differentiating (3.4) with respect to z and using the identity (1.6) in the resulting equation, we have

$$\gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta) = (\beta - p\alpha)p(z) + \alpha p^2(z) + \alpha z p'(z),$$

then

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z) \prec (\beta - p\alpha)p(z) + \alpha p^2(z) + \alpha z p'(z).$$

By setting $\theta(\omega) = \alpha\omega^2 + (\beta - p\alpha)\omega$ and $\varphi(\omega) = \alpha$, it is easily observed that $\theta(\omega)$ is analytic in C . Also, $\varphi(\omega)$ is analytic in $C \setminus \{0\}$ and that $\varphi(\omega) \neq 0$. Since $q(z)$ is convex univalent, it follows that

$$\operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{\theta'(q(z))}{\varphi(q(z))} \right\} = \operatorname{Re} \left\{ \frac{\beta - p\alpha}{\alpha} + 2q(z) \right\} > 0 \quad (z \in U).$$

Now Theorem 2 follows by applying Lemma 2. D

Putting $f(z) \equiv g(z)$ ($z \in U$) in Theorem 2, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 5. Let $\alpha \neq 0$, $\beta \geq 1$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$ and (4.1) holds true.

$$\text{Let } f \in A(p), \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)} \in H[q(0),1] \cap \mathcal{Q}.$$

Let

$$\begin{aligned} \gamma(f, \alpha, \beta) &= (\beta - (p+1)\alpha) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)} + \alpha(\lambda + p + 1) \frac{I_p^{\lambda+2}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)} \\ &\quad - \alpha(\lambda + p - 1) \left(\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)} \right)^2, \end{aligned}$$

be univalent in U and

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z) \prec \gamma(f, \alpha, \beta),$$

then

$$q(z) \prec \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)f(z)},$$

and q is the best subordinator.

Putting $a = \mu + p + 1$ ($\mu > -(p+1)$) and $c = 1$ in Theorem 2, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 6. Let $\alpha \neq 0$, $\beta > 0$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$ and (4.1) holds true.

$$\text{Let } f, g \in A(p), \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1,\mu}f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda,\mu}g(z)} \in H[q(0),1] \cap \mathcal{Q}. \text{ Let } \gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \text{ be univalent in } U \text{ and}$$

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z) \prec \gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta),$$

Where $\gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.7), then

$$q(z) \prec \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1,\mu}f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda,\mu}g(z)},$$

and q is the best subordinator.

Putting $a = \mu + p + 1$ ($\mu > -(p+1)$), $c = 1$ and $\lambda = \mu$ in Theorem 2, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 7. Let $\alpha \neq 0$, $\beta \geq 1$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$ and (4.1) holds true.

$$\text{Let } f, g \in A(p), \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(g)(z)} \in H[q(0),1] \cap \mathcal{Q}. \text{ Let } \gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \text{ be univalent in } U \text{ and}$$

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z) \prec \gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta),$$

Where $\gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.8), then

$$q(z) \prec \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(g)(z)},$$

and q is the best subdominant .

Putting $f(z) \equiv g(z)$ ($z \in U$) in Corollary 7, we obtain the following corollary .

Corollary 8. Let $\alpha \neq 0, \beta \geq 1$ and q be convex univalent in U with $q(0) = 1$

and (4.1) holds true. Let $f \in A(p), \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} \in H[q(0), 1] \cap Q$. Let $\gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta)$

be univalent in U and

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q(z) + \alpha q^2(z) + \alpha z q'(z) \prec \gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta),$$

where $\gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.9),

$$q(z) \prec \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} \quad (\mu > -p).$$

and q is the best subdominant .

We conclude this section by stating the following sandwich result.

Theorem 3. Let q_1 and q_2 be convex univalent in U , $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\beta \geq 1$. Suppose q_2 satisfies (3.1) and q_1 satisfies (4.1). Moreover, suppose

$$\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)} \in H[1,1] \cap Q$$

and $\gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is univalent in U . If $f, g \in A(p)$ satisfy

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q_1(z) + \alpha q_1^2(z) + \alpha z q_1'(z) \prec \gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - p\alpha)q_2(z) + \alpha q_2^2(z) + \alpha z q_2'(z),$$

where $\gamma(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.3), then

$$q_1(z) \prec \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^\lambda(a,c)g(z)} \prec q_2(z)$$

and q_1, q_2 are, respectively, the best subdominant and the best dominant.

By making use of Corollaries 2 and 6, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 9. Let q_1 and q_2 be convex univalent in U $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\beta \geq 1$. Suppose q_2 satisfies (3.1) and q_1 satisfies (4.1). Moreover, suppose

$$\frac{I_p^{\lambda+1,\mu}(a,c)f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda,\mu}(a,c)g(z)} \in H[1,1] \cap \mathcal{Q}$$

and $\gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is univalent in U . If $f, g \in A(p)$ satisfy

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q_1(z) + \alpha q_1^2(z) + \alpha z q_1'(z) \prec \gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - p\alpha)q_2(z) + \alpha q_2^2(z) + \alpha z q_2'(z),$$

where $\gamma_1(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.7), then

$$q_1(z) \prec \frac{I_p^{\lambda+1,\mu}f(z)}{I_p^{\lambda,\mu}g(z)} \prec q_2(z) \quad (\mu > -(p+1))$$

and q_1, q_2 are, respectively, the best subordinant and the best dominant.

By making use of Corollaries 3 and 7, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 10. Let q_1 and q_2 be convex univalent in U , $\alpha \neq 0$, and $\beta \geq 1$. . Suppose q_2 satisfies (3.1) and q_1 satisfies (4.1). Moreover, suppose

$$\frac{f(z)}{F_\mu(g)(z)} \in H[1,1] \cap \mathcal{Q}$$

$\gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is univalent in U . If $f, g \in A(p)$ satisfy

$$(\beta - p\alpha)q_1(z) + \alpha q_1^2(z) + \alpha z q_1'(z) \prec \gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - p\alpha)q_2(z) + \alpha q_2^2(z) + \alpha z q_2'(z),$$

where $\gamma_2(f, g, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.8), then

$$q_1(z) \prec \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(g)(z)} \prec q_2(z) \quad (\mu > -p)$$

and q_1, q_2 are, respectively, the best subordinant and the best dominant.

By making use of Corollaries 4 and 8, we obtain the following corollary.

Corollary 11. Let q_1 and q_2 be convex univalent in U , $\alpha \neq 0$ and $\beta \geq 1$. Suppose q_2 satisfies (3.1) and q_1 satisfies (4.1). Moreover, suppose

$$\frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} \in H[1,1] \cap \mathcal{Q}$$

And $\gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta)$ is univalent in U , $f \in A(p)$ satisfies

$$(\beta - \alpha)q_1(z) + \alpha q_1^2(z) + \alpha z q_1'(z) \prec \gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta) \prec (\beta - \alpha)q_2(z) + \alpha q_2^2(z) + \alpha z q_2'(z)$$

Where $\gamma_3(f, \alpha, \beta)$ is given by (3.9), then

$$q_1(z) \prec \frac{f(z)}{F_{\mu,p}(f)(z)} \prec q_2(z) \quad (\mu > -p)$$

and q_1, q_2 ,are respectively, the best subordinant and the best dominant.

Remark 2. Putting $p=1$, we obtain the results obtained by] Aouf and El-ashwah [2].

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